

GAS DRYING BY GLYCOL INJECTION

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Spray absorbers are widely used in Western Europe. Glycol is sprayed in a device whose diameter is close to the diameter of the supply gas pipeline. The efficiency of the process is determined by the degree of atomization of the solution, carried out by special nozzles. The atomized liquid creates a large phase contact surface, and high gas velocities (1-10 m/s) provide intense mass transfer and good distribution of particles in the flow. The best mass transfer occurs at high relative velocities of gas and droplets, which is achieved by injecting glycol towards the gas flow. The limit of crushing of liquid particles is the formation of fog, the release of particles of which is limited by existing separator designs. The optimal drying temperature is 15-30 °C. At low temperatures, the viscosity of glycols affects, at high temperatures, the vapor pressure of glycols increases and losses increase accordingly. It should be noted that glycol can be supplied to the injectors at temperatures above 30 °C, when its viscosity is low. During contact with gas, glycol takes on the temperature of the flow instantly, since its relative amount is insignificant. The drying process in each stage takes place in the nozzle cone mainly at the moment of formation of glycol drops and ends in the apparatus volume and the separator. To filter glycol, filters are provided that ensure the removal of suspended matter, particles of which are higher than 5 microns, since mechanical impurities clog the nozzles of the nozzles and cause foaming of the solution [1].

If the process of gas drying with glycol is carried out at low temperatures, then a 70-85 % solution of monoethylene glycol is used and the glycol is supplied by injection into the heat exchanger. This version of the gas drying scheme is used at the Orenburg Gas Processing Plant [2].

The glycol injection gas drying unit consists of three main units: glycol injection, three-phase separator and glycol regeneration unit. The drying efficiency depends on the gas/glycol contact area, i.e. on the degree of atomization of the desiccant. Special spray nozzles are used to finely spray glycol. As the gas moves inside the pipes, the liquid droplets become larger, which facilitates the separation of the dried gas and the saturated desiccant, as well as condensed hydrocarbons. Water desorption is carried out in a glycol regenerator.

Rice. 1. Schematic diagram of a gas drying installation with glycol injection:

1 - water refrigerator; 2 - water separator; 3 — glycol injection unit; 4 - heat exchanger; 5 - propane refrigerator; 6 - three-phase separator; 7 — weathering agent ; 8 - coil; 9 - stripping column; 10 - boiler; 11 — container for glycol; 12 - pump. Streams: I - raw gas; II - dried gas; III - weathering gases; IV – water vapor; V - hydrocarbon condensate; VI - saturated glycol; VII - regenerated glycol; VIII – fresh glycol; IX – water.

The compressed raw gas passes through the water cooler 1, the water separator 2, the glycol injection unit 3 and the heat exchanger 4. Then the gas enters the propane cooler 5 and then into the three-phase separator 6.

Dried gas and hydrocarbon condensate from the three-phase separator are sent for further processing, and saturated glycol is sent for regeneration. After passing through the weathering agent 7, glycol saturated with water enters the coil 8, mounted in the upper part of the stripping column 9. The coil cools and partially condenses water vapor in the column, which ensures irrigation of the column. The saturated glycol then enters the bottom of the stripping column through a heat exchanger. The stripped water vapor is discharged into the atmosphere, and the regenerated glycol enters the heat exchanger through the level regulator and then flows through the water cooler 1 into container 11.

From the container, regenerated glycol is pumped through pump 12 through the filter and sent to the injection unit.

The injection method in combination with gas cooling makes it possible to significantly lower the dew point, simultaneously dry the gas and the resulting gas condensate, and allows the use of glycols with a concentration of 70-80% as a desiccant . The disadvantage of the glycol injection drying method is the large

loss of desiccant with gas condensate. Gas drying by absorption minimizes glycol losses, but requires a higher degree of glycol recovery (up to 95-99%).

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